

The Availability of Smart Organization Dimensions in Technical Colleges in Palestine

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Abstract: *The objective of the study was to identify the dimensions of the smart organization in the technical colleges in Palestine, where the variables of the smart organizations included: "Strategic vision, culture of merit and excellence, incentive system." The analytical descriptive approach was used in the study. A questionnaire consisting of (39) paragraphs was used. The sample of the study was composed of (289) employees from the mentioned colleges. The response rate was (79.2%). The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of the smart organization and a relative weight (71.42%) according to the perspective of the employees of the technical colleges in Gaza Strip, where the field (culture of merit and skill) ranked first and with a relative weight (73.76%), in the second place came the field (strategic vision) and relative weight (72.62%). Finally, the area of the incentive program came in third and final rank with a relative weight of (67.91%). The researchers propose a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: To enhance the dimensions of the smart organization in the technical colleges by improving the incentive program, developing the strategic vision and then supporting the culture of merit and skill. Urging senior management and decision-makers to work in technical colleges to create, innovate, reward and support their creators.*

Keywords: Technical colleges, smart organizations, strategic vision, culture of merit and skill, incentive system, Palestine.

1. INTRODUCTION

The administration has become a prominent place in the life of human societies, because of the great benefits it brings to society, through the management of society develops and keeps pace with the changes of the era. The administration mobilizes energies, capabilities and capabilities and encourages them to innovate and innovate, especially as the age in which we live has become the era of the revolution of knowledge, the revolution of technology and the revolution of communication, and can only be dealt with through effective management. The environment of the organizations is changing from day to day, where change has become the only constant. The emergence of globalization and the great development in the field of information technology and the transformation of our age into the era of knowledge and progress, which led to increased competitiveness among organizations and became the survival of the better and smarter. Of the theories and management concepts that seek to make organizations more viable and competitive. Organizations that seek to develop themselves constantly and are able to bring about lasting change in the sustainability of their awareness of their goals and trends are described as organizations seeking to innovate and adapt to environmental changes with descriptions that have expressed this state of renewal, adaptation and survival from the self-evaluation organization to the Smart Organization. The organizations differ in their responsiveness to variables and their response to the challenges in their internal or external environment, and the extent to which they deliver high quality goods and services that are compatible with the expectations of customers and the aspirations of investors according to the quality and characteristics of their human resources.

The application of the smart organization principle is an excellent qualitative leap in the way organizations are run. Organizations learn and develop through themselves and the individuals they work with, and through experiences of other institutions and communities. The idea of a smart organization has a profound impact on how they think about the life of these organizations. The ideas that are built on them represent a challenge for the organization to use knowledge to develop competitive and expansionary strategies at the level of the organization. Local and global, and it seems important in the fact that what is taken from other communities is not necessarily applicable in another community because of the different culture, values and principles. Technical colleges have to operate and lead a kind of strategy that enables them to orient themselves towards the era of competition by turning them into intelligent organizations capable of adapting all their resources and resources to natural and abnormal changes. The present study is to identify technical colleges as intelligent organizations and their ability to achieve sustainability.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The problem of the study is the increasing number of universities and colleges in the Gaza Strip, which requires that there be conscious leadership capable of harnessing all possibilities to try to continue and keep up with the universities and international colleges and to achieve excellence in all fields. Based on the above, the problem of the study is determined by the following question: The availability of smart organization dimensions in technical colleges in Palestine?

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Highlighting the concept of smart organizations, identifying their components, clarifying the nature of their work and how they are being constructed.
2. Identify the reality of the components of smart organizations in the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip.
3. Statement of differences in the application of the principles of smart organization among technical colleges in the Gaza Strip.
4. To promote technical education and enhance its function in the service of society.
5. Outcomes and recommendations contribute to the development and resolution of problems facing technical education.
6. The conclusion of the conclusions and recommendations of the administrative leaders in the higher education institutions in general and the technical colleges in particular, may contribute to improve their performance and stimulate them to apply the philosophy of the organization smart, which contributes to the development of technical education.

4. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The importance of this study stems from the following points:

1. Most of the studies related to the concept of smart organization were concentrated in Western environments, where administrative concepts and performance measurement tools developed rapidly, while the current study dealt with the Arab environment, specifically the Palestinian environment.
2. Draw attention to the importance of smart organization, and emphasize the dissemination of the organization's smart culture and follow up its applications in technical colleges.
3. The study focuses on the smart organization in the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip, in order to be appropriate and compatible with their needs, achieving their strategic objectives and serving other business organizations.
4. See the reality of smart organization in technical colleges, and monitor the strengths and weaknesses in their applications in these institutions.
5. To enrich the Arab academic arena with new research studies and partnerships in the fields of administrative development.

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

In order to provide an appropriate answer to the questions posed, the study seeks to test the validity of the following hypotheses:

H01: There is a high level of elements of smart organizations in the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip.

H02: There are statistically significant differences at the level of a ≤ 0.05 in the dimensions of the smart organization according to the macro variable.

H03: There are statistically significant differences at the level of a ≤ 0.05 in the dimensions of the smart organization according to the functional level variable.

6. RESEARCH LIMITS AND SCOPE

1. **Subject Limit (Academic):** The study was limited in its objective to study the availability of smart organization dimensions in technical colleges in Palestine
2. **Human Limit:** The study was conducted on the responses of workers in the technical colleges under study.
3. **Institutional Limit:** This study was conducted on the major technical colleges in the Gaza Governorates (Palestine Technical College - Dair Al-Balah, University College of Science and Technology, Gaza Community Training College, Al-Azhar College of Intermediate Studies, University College of Applied Sciences, Al-Aqsa Society College).
4. **Spatial Limit:** The study was conducted in the State of Palestine and was limited to technical colleges in the Gaza Strip (Palestine Technical College - Dair Al-Balah, University College of Science and Technology, GTC), Al-Azhar University College of Applied Sciences, Al-Aqsa Society College).
5. **Time Limits:** The study was conducted and preliminary data were collected about the technical colleges and statistical analyzes conducted during the year (2018). So it represents the reality at this time.

7. RESEARCH TERMINOLOGY

- **Technician:** A person who occupies a middle position between the engineer and the technologist on the one hand and the skilled worker on the other. He has the task of applying the technical practices. He has the scientific knowledge, professional skills and technical expertise that helps him to diagnose the problems and develop the details. He is responsible for transforming the engineer designs into an integrated production process (Al-Shahry, 1995). The task of the technical team is the middle jobs in the production sites and intermediate administrative works and they form the mainstay of the production and service process because they are professionally considered as the operational working link between the various categories of specialists of engineers, trade and others and among the categories of technical workers who work in all the institutions on which the economy is based (Al-Saeed, 2006).
- **Technical colleges:** are regular educational institutions with duration of between 2-3 years after high school and without first-degree students (Mustafa, 2001). Technical colleges have recently been interested in analytical abilities and innovative skills as well as more Modern technologies, adaptation, operation and maintenance, and the training of technicians to absorb the rapid and complex transformations in order to meet the needs of the production and service sectors. Hence, many countries have started to award university degrees and masters and doctorate degrees such faculty's High technology in the United Arab Emirates, which grants bachelor's degree in Engineering Technology (Al-Issa, 2004).
- **Technical Education:** This is the type of formal higher education that includes educational preparation and imparting the skills and technical knowledge that are carried out by regular educational institutions not less than two years after secondary school to prepare a workforce in different disciplines (Al-Abd, 2001).
The researchers defines technical education as: education that earns individuals the knowledge, skills and trends that qualify them to join the labor market in a technical work and study two years after high school.
- **Smart organizations** are the use of high technology and some refer to the intelligence of individuals in the organizations resulting from the processes of learning and training. There are many views, both of which are characterized by the fact that the smart organization is a mixture of the intelligence of individuals and the use of modern technology (Al-Faraj and Al-Zubayr, 2011).
- **The operational definition of the Smart Organization** is the product of technology application processes in the face of the challenge of business development, through the successful alignment between the organization and the environment and the development of competitive advantages based on a strategic vision and a culture of merit and efficiency with an effective incentive system.

8. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Study of (El Talla et al., 2017) aimed to identify the reality of technical education in Palestine. The analytical descriptive method was used in the study. A questionnaire which consisted of 41 paragraphs was distributed randomly to the technical colleges in Gaza Strip. Random sample of (275) employees of these colleges were used, and the response rate was (74.5%). The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of technical education with a relative weight of 76.07%. The ranking and relative weight was as follows: Technical education institutions: 79.51%, graduates of technical education 75.75%, Labor market and local community 72.96%. The researchers propose a number of recommendations, the most important of which is: the need to pay attention to technical education in line with the National Strategic Plan for Higher Education by moving towards technical education. The importance of offering special courses in all technical education programs in these colleges. The researchers urged more future studies that address the same variables as the current study and apply them to other sectors.
- Study of (El Talla et al., 2017) aimed to identify the creative environment and its relation to the graceful management of the technical colleges operating in Gaza Strip. The analytical descriptive method was used through a questionnaire which was randomly distributed to 289 employees of the technical colleges in Gaza Strip with a total number of (1168) employees and a response rate equal to (79.2%) of the sample study. The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of the creative environment with a relative weight of (75.19%). It also showed a high level of creative environment where the ranking and relative weight was as follows: Fluency (76.86%), Sensation of problems (74.89%), Flexibility (74.59%) and originality (74.41%). The results showed that the technical colleges achieved a high level of agile management with a relative weight of 76.69% and a high level of agile management. (79.56%), responding to customer requirements (79.14%), reducing costs (75.68%), maximizing competitiveness and profitability (74.59%), Improve service (74.52%), and the results showed a statistically significant difference relationship between the dimensions of the creative environment and management in agile technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The researchers suggested a number of recommendations, the most important of which is the need to enhance the dimensions of the creative

environment by working to improve the abilities of the faculties in fluency, flexibility, originality, sensitivity to problems and the importance of increasing attention to the dimensions of achieving the graceful management because of their role in the development of technical education departments and sustainability. Develop agile management mechanisms and applications in terms of reducing waste, reducing costs, improving service, responding to customer requirements, and maximizing competitiveness and profitability, commensurate with the capabilities of these colleges.

- Study of (Abu Naser et al., 2017) aimed to identify the technical education and its role in promoting entrepreneurship in Gaza Strip. The analytical descriptive method was used in the study. A questionnaire was composed of (41) items and distributed randomly by the technical colleges in Gaza Strip using stratified random sample of (275) employees from the mentioned colleges, and the response rate was (74.5%). The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of technical education with a relative weight of 76.07%. The ranking and relative weights were as follows: Technical education institutions: 79.51%, graduates of technical education 75.75% Labor market and local community 72.96%. The results of the study showed that the technical colleges achieved a high level of promotion of entrepreneurship with a relative weight of 73.45%. Where the ranking and relative weights were as follows: competitive assault (76.65%), creative orientation (74.96%), preparedness (74.07%) and risk (68.39%). The results also confirmed a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of technical education and the promotion of entrepreneurship in technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The results also confirmed a statistically significant impact of technical education on the promotion of entrepreneurship in the technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The researchers proposed a number of recommendations, the most important: the need to go to technical education because of its role in the promotion of entrepreneurship, the importance of linking technical education and promoting entrepreneurship to the Palestinian society in general and the Gaza Strip in particular, the need to pay attention to technical education in line with the National Strategic Plan for Higher Education by moving towards technical education, and the importance of urging decision-makers in technical colleges to promote interest in leadership and to put their own courses in all technical education programs in these colleges. The researchers urged further studies of the same variables as the current study of entrepreneurship and their application to other sectors.
- Study of (Abu Naser et al., 2017) aimed to identify the social networks and their role in achieving the effectiveness of electronic marketing for technical colleges in the Gaza Strip, which included variables of social networks and their role in electronic marketing, as well as the recognition of the existence of differences of statistical significance in the attitudes of respondents towards the variables of the study, and using a descriptive analytical approach in the study. A questionnaire of 50 items was randomly distributed among the technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The sample of the study was composed of (275) employees of these colleges. The response rate was 74.5%. The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of social networks and a relative weight (74.15%). There is a high level of social networking areas (site management (74.91%), content of the site: (73.38%)). The technical colleges achieved a high level of use of electronic marketing, where the total relative weight (70.24%). There is a high level of e-marketing (Electronic advertising (71.75%), electronic promotion (74.75%), news groups (66.03%), and communication with the audience (student) (68.73%)). There is a statistically significant relationship between the organization's smart dimensions and sustainability in the technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The results also confirmed that there is a statistically significant impact of social networks in e-marketing in the technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The researchers proposed a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: Adopting dealing with the various social media sites as a reality on the Palestinian and Arab technical colleges, using them in accordance with the objectives of the technical colleges. The need to direct marketing through social networks and the exploitation of this network in marketing through them, the follow-up of the pages of the colleges and open the door of dialogue, communication, and respond to all inquiries. Technical colleges should put electronic marketing in their strategic marketing plan.
- Study of (El Talla et al., 2017) aimed at identify technical colleges as smart organizations and their relation to sustainability. The variables of smart organizations included: "Strategic vision, culture of merit and excellence, incentive system" and its relation to sustainability, which included three main dimensions (innovation, processes, and environmental aspects of the community). The questionnaire was composed of (39) items, which were randomly distributed to the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip. The sample of the study consisted of 289 employees from the mentioned colleges. The response rate was (79.2%). The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of the smart organization and relative weight (71.42%) according to the perspective of the employees of the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip. Where the field (culture of merit and skill) ranked first and with relative weight (73.76%), followed by strategic vision and relative weight (72.62%), and finally

came the area (incentive program) in the third and last place and a relative weight (67.91%). The results of the study showed that the technical colleges achieved a level high in sustainability in its operations with total relative weight (73.33%). Where the field (environmental aspects of society) came first and with relative weight (73.97%), followed by innovation and relative weight (73.10%), and finally came the field (operations) ranked third and last and relative weight (72.92%). The results confirmed a statistically significant relationship between the organization's smart dimensions and sustainability in the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip. The researchers propose a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: to enhance the dimensions of the smart organization in the technical colleges by improving the incentive program, developing the strategic vision and then supporting the culture of merit and skill. And increasing attention to the dimensions of achieving sustainability because of their role in the development and sustainability of technical education through the promotion and improvement of operations in technical colleges. He urged senior management and decision-makers to work in technical colleges to create, innovate and reward and support their creators.

- Study of (Al-Kasasbeh et al., 2016), which aims to study the effect of intelligent organization characteristics: a clear strategic vision, a culture of merit, and a supportive incentive system on social and environmental performance. The results confirm that the level of importance of respondents' perceptions of the elements of the characteristics of smart organization in Jordan Phosphate Mines Company is medium. The importance of respondents' perceptions of the elements of social performance was moderate, with the exception of paragraphs relating to the introduction of assistance to poor families in the community, respect for society, customs and traditions, contribution to training university students and provision of health care for the company, employees and their families. And that the level of importance of respondents' perceptions about the elements of environmental performance is moderate. And that there is no statistical impact of the clear strategic vision and culture of merit on the social performance and environmental performance of the Jordanian phosphate mining company. And that there is a statistical impact of the system of incentives supporting the social and environmental performance of Jordan Phosphate Mines Company.
- Study of (Al-Taei et al., 2016) which aims to identify the relationship and impact between the management of wisdom through its dimensions (knowledge, meditation, conscience) and the sustainability of organizations through their dimensions (competitive advantage, legitimacy, social responsibility). The research problem identified a major question as to whether there is a role to manage the wisdom of the sustainability of organizations. The research community was one of the leaders at Kufa University. The random sample was chosen in 38 university leaders. The results of the study confirm that wisdom represents the summit of investment knowledge and it represents diligence within the space of knowledge is not limited, and specifically in the spaces of the knowledge gap in which there is no clear text. And the importance of reflection and insight into the issue of the hierarchical relation of data, information, knowledge, and wisdom. And to develop them on an objective basis, which maximizes the use of the advantages of the two sides in the process of thinking and in administrative applications.
- Study of (Pharaoh et al., 2015) aimed at answering a number of intellectual and practical questions, most notably the nature of the relationship between the strategy of entrepreneurship and building in the mobile telecommunications companies in Iraq? Are managers aware of their importance based on their priorities? And what is its influential role in developing the model of its smart organizations. Where it aimed to answer these questions by clarifying the conceptual implications of these variables.
- Study of (Al-Abadi, 2012) which aims to study organizations that aspire to be smart organizations, smart organizations are only able to succeed and excel in the environment of business with high competition, and this environment, which continued to change resulted in the search for organizational intelligence facing those changes, which requires the management of organizations to devote much of its time to ensuring that it and all its members are committed to achieving (strategic intelligence, tactical intelligence, operational intelligence), which represents organizational intelligence levels.

Comment on previous studies

By reviewing the literature available to the researchers, and related to the subject of the current study, it is possible to summarize what distinguishes the current study from the previous studies referred to according to the areas described as follows:

1. **Study Environment:** Previous studies related to the concept of the organization or some of its dimensions in Western environments in which the concepts of management and tools related to the measurement of performance and standards have been accelerated, while the current study was carried out in the Arab

environment and specifically in the Palestinian environment, Technology has been significantly improved over the past years to identify the extent to which they are applied to the organization's smart principles.

2. **The nature of the study society:** The society of the previous study is chosen by selecting a particular study as a case study or survey covering a period of time (several years) and leading companies in a variety of industries. The current study community (technical colleges) in Gaza Strip is not a variety, Local and important technology.
3. **Topics:** The majority of previous studies or presented the characteristics of the organization smart and how they can be employed to maintain the excellence and continuity of those organizations, and the reasons for the failure of some organizations and the relationship of these characteristics to failure, while the current study tried to identify the availability of smart organization dimensions in technical colleges in Palestine.
4. The present study has attempted to provide a scientific reference, data and information related to the characteristics of the technical colleges in Gaza Strip, which will help in their development and improvement in the future.
5. The current study highlights the extent to which the technical colleges in particular (Palestine Technical College - Deir Al-Balah, University College of Science and Technology, Gaza Community Training College, Al-Azhar University College of Applied Sciences, Al-Azhar University College) In particular the concept of the smart organization and its principles.
6. Several previous studies have relied on the division of smart organizations into 9 dimensions such as Matheson and Matheson (2001), 7 dimensions, 5 dimensions. The present study has been based on (3) dimensions given the specificities of technical colleges; its size is compared to large organizations that depend on the areas and dimensions of the smart organization.

9. THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

Smart Organization

The concept of smart organizations emerged as a response to the increase in environmental disruptions. Smart organizations include ongoing surveys and adaptations to the environment rather than surveys conducted through annual planning and review. They are a continuous process that includes the efforts of strategic managers to bring about a successful match between the organization and the environment by developing competitive advantages based on organizational intelligence and focusing on the principles of smart organizations.

The emergence of the smart organization as a contemporary concept, which emphasized the research and development processes in the various organizations and then took this concept from within the organization to include the evolution of the organization as a whole of the necessity gained from within the organizations so the development of this concept to become a comprehensive represents the smart organization, (Teresko, 2006).

The concept of smart organization has also begun by (Quinn, 2005) focused on the management approach that applies technology and new service models to meet the challenge of developing business performance.

Quinn (2005) assumes that thought is the central and essential resource in the production and delivery of services. Thus, the concept of smart organization is clearly associated with the concept of knowledge management. The concept of "smart organization" later evolved to focus more on knowledge management, acquisition, learning and adaptation; it is an organization that leads knowledge and integrates knowledge management with the other effective management tools used (Poulsen & Arthur, 2005)

The researchers believe that Smart Organization is the product of continuous processes that apply technology and new service models to meet the challenge of developing business performance. The strategic managers' efforts include creating a successful match between the organization and the environment through the development of competitive advantages based on a strategic vision, culture of merit, which would then include the evolution of the Organization as a whole, knowledge-driven and integrated in the management of knowledge with the range of other effective management tools used.

Smart Organization Dimensions

Matheson & Matheson (2001) reported that smart organizations can be divided into 9 dimensions. In this study, 3 dimensions will be used because of the small size and specificity of technical colleges compared to large organizations. The researchers relied on the study of the dimensions of the smart organization on a number of previous studies and models, including Al-Kasasbeh et al. (2016) and Mark (2009).

1. First dimension: strategic vision

- Vision must provide clarity of purpose.

2. Second dimension: culture of merit and skill

There are three things that must be met in a culture of merit and skill:

- Listening to employee opinions.
- Non-punishment of employees on dissenting opinion.
- It is OK to share extremist ideas, even if they do not work.

3. Third dimension: incentive system

Three parts of the FAO incentive plan will be discussed.

- Strengthening the values of the Organization.
- Develop an implicit culture that individuals appreciate.
- Measure performance correctly.

10. STUDY PROCEDURES

First- Research Methodology

This study is based on the analytical descriptive approach to describe and describe the phenomenon to be studied as it exists. In fact, researchers in this approach are considering the study of tools, phenomena and practices existing and available for study and measurement as they are, without the intervention of the researchers in their course, and researchers can interact with them and describe them and analyze them scientifically and objectively.

The study relies on two basic types of data:

1. **Initial Data:** The study was carried out in the field by distributing questionnaires to study the vocabulary of the study, collecting and gathering the necessary information in the subject of the study, and then unloading and analyzing it using the statistical program (SPSS) and using the appropriate statistical tests in order to arrive at indications of value and indicators that support the subject of the study. And some personal interviews conducted by the researchers with those involved in order to obtain some undocumented data in writing and to clarify some views.
2. **Secondary data:** through the review of books, periodicals, special publications, scientific and professional journals related to the subject of the study, and any references contribute to enrich the study in a scientific way, and the researchers through the use of secondary sources in the study to identify the foundations and scientific methods sound in writing studies, A general overview of the latest developments that took place in the field of study.

Second- Study Population:

The study population consists of all the staff working in technical colleges in Gaza Strip (Palestine Technical College - Dair Al-Balah, University College of Science and Technology, Gaza Training Community College, Al-Azhar College of Studies, University College of Applied Sciences, Al-Aqsa Society College). The study population may be (1168) of the employees of the technical colleges under study as follows:

Table 1: illustrates the study population

The College	Number Of Employees	The Ratio%
Palestine Technical College	193	%16.52
University College of Science and Technology	204	%17.47
Gaza Training Community College	119	%10.19
College of Intermediate Studies- Al-Azhar	184	%15.75
University College of Applied Sciences	335	%28.68
Al-Aqsa Society College	133	%11.39
Total	1168	%100

Source: Prepared by researchers by reference to the statistical book and the annual statistical guide for Palestinian higher education institutions, Ministry of Education and Higher Education (2016)

Third- The study sample:

1. A survey sample was used by the researchers to verify the validity and reliability of these tools. The sample size was 32 employees.
2. The sample is random and consists of (298) employees of these colleges. The response rate was 79.2%.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents from the sample of the study

Personal Data	Category	The Number	The Ratio%
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Career Level	Dean / Vice	5	%2.18
	Head of Academic Section	19	%8.44
	Head of Administrative Section	23	%10.04
	the Administrative	82	%35.80
	Full time lecturer	74	%32.3
	Part time lecturer	26	%11.35
	Total	229	%100
The college	Palestine Technical College	30	%13
	University College of Science and Technology	22	%10
	Gaza Training Community College	31	%13.5
	College of Intermediate Studies- Al-Azhar	48	%21
	University College of Applied Sciences	46	%20
	Al-Aqsa Society College	52	%22.5
	Total	229	%100

Table 2 shows that:

As for the career level, the Dean / Vice category came at (2.18%), the Academic Head of Section (8.44%), the Head of Administrative Section (10.04%) and the Administrative Category (35.80%). On the keenness of technical colleges to attract administrators able to promote their colleges and serve the students and facilitate them, and the category of full-time lecturer in the second place and by (32.3%) and this indicates the keenness of technical colleges to provide a scientific atmosphere specialized in the presence of cadres full-time academic ability to develop Students and give them a sufficient amount of academic sciences systematically and correctly, as the Part - time lecturer (11.35%) as technical colleges still need more specialists in different fields.

As for the college variable, Al-Aqsa Society College came in first place with a percentage of (22.5%) as it is a government college. Among the general orientations of the Ministry of Education is the orientation towards technical education. Therefore, there is a keenness from the Ministry to provide government colleges with the needs they need. The Faculty of Intermediate Studies - Al Azhar ranked second by (21%), the University College of Applied Sciences came third (20%), followed by the Gaza Community Training Society, followed by the fourth (13.5%), then the Technical College of Palestine, which received a percentage (13%), thus, the University College of Science and Technology ranked second (10%).

Fourthly- Study tool:

Since the nature of hypotheses and the variables included in them are the ones that control the selection of the appropriate tool. Accordingly, the researchers have prepared a scale for the study that fits its objectives and hypotheses, which is the measure of the smart organizations in the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip. The process of designing and preparing the study scale has gone through several stages and steps:

1. See the literature of smart organizations, and previous studies on the subject of the current study.
2. Collect and define scale paragraphs.
3. Formulation of the standard expressions according to the study sample.
4. Set the meter instructions.
5. How to correct the meter.
6. Conduct a study of stability and honesty of the scale.

How to correct the meter:

The five-dimensional Likert scale was used to measure respondents' responses to the questionnaire sections according to the following table:

Table 3: The degrees of the five-dimensional Likert scale

Response	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Class	1	2	3	4	5

Validate the measure: The researchers calculated the validity of the meter in the following ways:

1. **Virtual honesty:** The researchers verified the authenticity of the tool ostensibly by presenting it to a group of PhD holders in Business Administration (8). The apparent honesty indicates the general appearance of the test in terms of its relevance to the subjects, the relevance of the phrase to the field, and the clarity of the wording and instructions.
2. **Internal consistency:** The researchers calculated the validity of the internal consistency of the scale by finding the correlation coefficients between each field and the total score of the scale. The researchers conducted

honesty and persistence on a sample of 32 employees by finding correlation coefficients for each paragraph in the field to which they belong. The following tables:

Table 4: Validity coefficients for each paragraph with the total score of its field in the smart organizations scale

Strategic Vision			Culture Of Merit And Craftsmanship			Incentive Program		
Paragraph Number	Honesty Coefficient	Level Of Significance	Paragraph Number	Honesty Coefficient	Level Of Significance	Paragraph Number	Honesty Coefficient	Level Of Significance
1	0.749	0.01	1	0.842	0.01	1	0.791	0.01
2	0.751	0.01	2	0.867	0.01	2	0.719	0.01
3	0.797	0.01	3	0.875	0.01	3	0.767	0.01
4	0.653	0.01	4	0.803	0.01	4	0.759	0.01
5	0.780	0.01	5	0.841	0.01	5	0.849	0.01
6	0.871	0.01	6	0.776	0.01	6	0.690	0.01
7	0.783	0.01	7	0.858	0.01	7	0.842	0.01

Stability of the scale:

The concept of stability means the ability of the test to give the same grades or values to the same individual or individuals if the measurement process is repeated. To ensure the stability of the scale, the researchers used the following methods:

1. **The method of split-half:** by calculating the correlation coefficient between the individual questions and marital questions, and obtained the stability coefficients shown in the following table.

Table 5: Stability coefficient of smart organizations

No.	Field	Number of Item	Correlation Coefficient Before Adjustment	Correlation Coefficient After Adjustment	Level Of Significance
1.	Strategic vision	7	0.799	0.855	Sig. at 0.01
2.	Culture of merit and craftsmanship	7	0.901	0.916	Sig. at 0.01
3.	Incentive Program	7	0.794	0.863	Sig. at 0.01

From the previous table, it is clear that the stability coefficients in all midterm segments were high, indicating that the questionnaire has a high degree of stability.

2. **Alpha Cronbach's coefficient of persistence:** The researchers performed alpha-cronbach's persistence coefficient between the terms of each field separately, as shown in the following table:

Table 6: shows the coefficients of Alpha Cronbach's stability for each of the domains of the smart organizations scale

No.	Field	Coefficient Of Alpha-Cronbach Stability
1.	Strategic vision	0.898
2.	Culture of merit and craftsmanship	0.929
3.	Incentive Program	0.884

The overall correlation coefficient (0.956), which is a high stability coefficient, indicates the strength and validity of the scale. The researchers noted that the coefficients of the coefficients of the coefficients Pearson's correlations correlate with the results of alpha-cronbach's persistence coefficient.

Fifthly- Statistical Methods:

The computer was used in the statistical processing, especially the statistical packages program (SPSS), where all the data obtained by the researchers and then the results were extracted through the scientific equations necessary for this and the most important used in this study:

1. Averages, frequencies, standard deviations and percentages.
2. Spearman Brown's correlation coefficient for the equal half - division, and the Cronbach alpha factor to determine the stability of the resolution.

3. Pearson correlation coefficient to measure the relationship between variables.
4. T test for differences between averages.
5. One way Anova test

11. TEST QUESTIONS AND STUDY HYPOTHESES

The five-Likert scale was used to prepare the study instrument. The study adopted the following table to judge the trend when using the pentagram.

Table 7: Scale of measurements used in this study

Method The Level	SMA	Relative weight%
Very Low	Less than (1.80)	Less than 36.00%
Low	From (1.80): (2.59)	From 36.00: 51.90%
Medium	From (2.60): (3.39)	From 52.00: 67.90%
High	From (3.40): (4.19)	From 68.00: 83.90%
Very High	Greater than (4.20)	Greater than 84.00%

The first hypothesis test, which states:

There is a high level of smart organization elements in technical colleges in the Gaza Strip.

To test this hypothesis, the researchers resorted to frequencies, averages, standard deviation, percentages, order and value of "T". The results were as shown in the following tables:

Table 8: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentages, Order, and Value of "T" of Sample Responses in Strategic Vision

No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	"T" Value	Relative Weight%	Item Order	Morality P- Value
1.	The work environment is analyzed and the methods used to identify opportunities and threats	3.73	0.827	13.298	74.60%	1	0.000
2.	The strategy is formulated on the basis of the needs and expectations of current and future stakeholders.	3.69	0.795	13.026	73.80%	3	0.000
3.	The College constantly develops and reviews policy and strategy	3.73	0.880	12.443	74.60%	2	0.000
4.	The college uses different techniques to generate decision-making alternatives.	3.58	0.887	9.823	71.60%	5	0.000
5.	The College addresses future risks through contingency planning, risk analysis, scenarios and plans.	3.53	0.892	8.898	70.60%	7	0.000
6.	The college strategy is measured and evaluated internally and externally.	3.61	0.819	11.101	72.20%	4	0.000
7.	The senior management is transparent about the strategic direction of the college.	3.57	0.994	8.588	71.40%	6	0.000
Total domain		3.6312	0.71437	13.341	72.62%		0.000

The tabular value of "T" is at a degree of freedom (228) and at the level of significance (0.05) = 1.65

The tabular value of "T" is at the degree of freedom (228) and at the level of significance (0.01) = 2.34

Table (8) shows that through the test of the related samples, all the areas of the strategic field of view were calculated as "T" greater than the "T". Thus, there is a statistical significance of the relative weight of the field. The first paragraph (analyzing the work environment and methods used to identify opportunities and threats) ranked first with a relative weight of (74.60%) which shows the interest of technical colleges to analyze the work environment and identify the risks, while the fifth paragraph (the college to address future risks through contingency planning and

risk analysis and the development of scenarios and plans) in the last place with a relative weight (70.60%), the total score of the field obtained a relative weight and its value (72.62%) which is high, ie, there is a high level of strategic vision in technical colleges. The researchers explain this finding that the rapidly changing environment, especially in the technical field, and the intense competition as a result of the increasing number of technical colleges have made the colleges work to build a strategic vision that matches these large and rapid challenges.

Al-Abadi (2012) agreed that it requires management to devote most of its time to ensuring that it and all its members are committed to achieving (strategic intelligence, tactical intelligence, operational intelligence. (Mark, 2009), which stressed that there are three characteristics necessary for the smart organization First: a clear strategic vision Second: smart organizations have a culture of merit that respects the ideas of each individual Third: smart organizations have incentive programs that support the vision and culture The results varied with the study of (Al-Kasasbeh et al., 2016) showed that the level of significance of the respondents' perceptions The importance of respondents' perceptions of the elements of social performance was moderate.

Table 9: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentage, Order, and Value of "T" of the Responses of Sample Members in the Field of Culture of Merit and Proficiency

No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	"T" Value	Relative Weight%	Item Order	Morality P- Value
1.	The College uses state-of-the-art information systems.	3.88	0.921	14.381	77.60%	1	0.000
2.	The information systems used in the College support a broad exchange of information and knowledge.	3.76	0.900	12.755	75.20%	2	0.000
3.	The college has a flat organizational structure that supports the empowerment of workers	3.64	0.972	9.947	72.80%	5	0.000
4.	The systems used in the college enable employees to perform their work efficiently and effectively.	3.75	0.908	12.504	75.00%	3	0.000
5.	The College provides a strategic decision-making system in a timely manner.	3.63	0.966	9.825	72.60%	6	0.000
6.	There is an appropriate creative environment in the college.	3.49	1.012	7.230	69.80%	7	0.000
7.	The College has appropriate organizational values.	3.67	0.955	10.561	73.40%	4	0.000
Total domain		3.6878	0.80432	12.912	73.76%		0.000

The tabular value of "T" is at a degree of freedom (228) and at the level of significance (0.05) = 1.65

The tabular value of "T" is at the degree of freedom (228) and at the level of significance (0.01) = 2.34

Table (9) shows that all the paragraphs of the culture of merit and proficiency were calculated as "T" values greater than the value of "T" Thus, there is a statistical significance of the relative weight of the paragraphs of this field, so the first paragraph (the college uses modern information systems and advanced work) ranked first with a relative weight of (77.60%) this indicates the extent of the development of MIS in the technical colleges, while the sixth paragraph (there is a suitable creative environment in the college) ranked last with relative weight (69.80%), the total score of the field obtained a relative weight and its value (73.76%) which is a high degree, that is, there is a level of culture of merit and high proficiency in technical colleges. The researchers explain this result that the colleges in the study is the largest and oldest colleges in the Gaza Strip, and thus accumulated experience, and developed information systems and thus turned into the adoption of flat organizational structures, its internal systems have also been developed to accommodate rapid changes in internal and external environments.

Al-Kasasbeh et al. (2016) agreed that the level of importance of respondents' perceptions of the elements of the characteristics of smart organization in Jordan Phosphate Mines Company is medium. Al-Taei et al. (2016) which emphasized the importance of reflection and insight in the issue of the hierarchical relation of data, information, knowledge, and wisdom. And to develop them on an objective basis, which maximizes the use of the advantages of the two sides in the process of thinking and in administrative applications.

The results differed with Al-Kasasbeh et al. (2016), which confirms that there is a statistical effect of the system of incentives supporting the social and environmental performance of Jordan Phosphate Mines Company.

Table 10: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentages, Order, and Value of "T" of Sample Responses in the Incentive Program

No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	"T" Value	Relative Weight%	Item Order	Morality P- Value
1.	The incentive system in the college is fair and equitable	3.18	1.127	2.421	63.60%	6	0.016
2.	The College provides a suitable salary for its employees.	3.51	1.067	7.200	70.20%	2	0.000
3.	The College provides end of service benefits.	3.50	1.021	7.298	70.00%	3	0.000
4.	The College provides incentives for employees.	3.12	1.108	1.628	62.40%	7	0.105
5.	College allows employees to participate in the development of suggestions and solutions.	3.50	0.966	7.748	70.00%	4	0.000
6.	The College promotes the development of employees' own capabilities.	3.41	1.016	5.987	68.20%	5	0.000
7.	The College contributes to the development of human relations between employees.	3.59	1.042	8.463	71.80%	1	0.000
Total domain		3.3953	0.84303	7.064	67.91%		0.000

The tabular value of "T" is at a degree of freedom (228) and at the level of significance (0.05) = 1.65

The tabular value of "T" is at the degree of freedom (228) and at the level of significance (0.01) = 2.34

Table (10) shows that through the test of the relevant samples, all the terms of the incentive program area were the value of the calculated "T" greater than the tabular "T" value except for the fourth paragraph, thus, there is a statistical significance of the relative weight of the paragraphs of this area, so the seventh paragraph (the college contributes to the development of human relations among workers) ranked first with a relative weight of (71.80%) this confirms the great role of technical colleges in the development of human relations between employees, which creates a great incentive for them to achieve, while the fourth paragraph (the availability of college incentives for workers) in the last place with a relative weight (62.40%) which is a medium degree, and the total score of the field has a relative weight and its value (67.91%) which is a middle degree approaching the high, ie there is an average incentive program level at the technical colleges. The researchers explain this result of the disparity in the incentive system between the general technical colleges (University College of Applied Sciences, Al-Dasat Middle School - Al-Azhar) on the one hand, which depends on the program of the unified cadre of universities, and the incentive system in the government colleges (Al Aqsa, University College of Science and Technology, Technical College of Palestine) and linked to the system of government salaries of institutions of higher education, in addition to the financial crisis experienced by universities and colleges in the Gaza Strip due to the difficult economic situation in the Gaza Strip.

Al-Kasasbeh et al. (2016) agreed that the level of importance of respondents' perceptions of the elements of social performance is moderate, and Mark (2009), which confirmed the results that there are three essential characteristics of the smart organization: a clear strategic vision. Second: Smart organizations have a culture of merit that respects the ideas of each individual. Third: Smart organizations have incentive programs that support vision and culture. The researchers conclude that these three qualities are a necessity.

Table 11: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentage, Order, and Value of "T" of Responses of Sample Members in All Fields and Grade

No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	"T" Value	Relative Weight%	Item Order	Morality P- Value
1.	Strategic vision	3.6312	0.71437	13.341	72.62%	2	0.000
2.	Culture of merit and craftsmanship	3.6878	0.80432	12.912	73.76%	1	0.000

3.	Incentive Program	3.3953	0.84303	7.064	67.91%	3	0.000
Overall degree of smart organizations		3.5710	0.71424	12.072	71.42%		0.000

The tabular value of "T" is at a degree of freedom (228) and at the level of significance (0.05) = 1.65

The tabular value of "T" is at the degree of freedom (228) and at the level of significance (0.01) = 2.34

Table (11) shows that in all fields the calculated "T" value is greater than the "T" value of the table, Thus, there is a statistical significance of the relative weight of these areas, so the second field (culture of merit and skill) ranked first with a relative weight of (73.76%), while the strategic vision came second with relative weight (72.62%), then the area (incentive program) in the third place and the relative weight (67.91%), the total score of the smart organizations has a relative weight and value (71.42%) which is high, that is, there is a high level of elements of smart organizations in the technical colleges under study, this indicates the validity of the first hypothesis. The researchers explain this finding that technical colleges and their field of work are naturally intelligent organizations that have a culture of merit and skill and have a strategic vision, and provide employees with an incentive program that promotes organizational intelligence.

The results differed with the study of Al-Kasasbeh et al. (2016), which showed an average level of the organization's smart elements, and researchers attributed this difference to the different environment between the two studies.

The second hypothesis test, which states:

Second hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences at the level of $\alpha \leq 0.05$ in the dimensions of the smart organization according to the macro variable.

To test this hypothesis, the analysis of mono-variance was used as in the following table:

Table 12: Analysis of the single variance of One Way Anova to find differences in the dimensions of the organization smart according to the macro change

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Strategic vision	Between Groups	13.401	5	2.680	5.808	.000
	Within Groups	102.444	222	.461		
	Total	115.845	227			
Culture of merit and craftsmanship	Between Groups	18.417	5	3.683	6.367	.000
	Within Groups	128.435	222	.579		
	Total	146.852	227			
Incentive Program	Between Groups	15.077	5	3.015	4.579	.001
	Within Groups	145.541	221	.659		
	Total	160.618	226			
Overall degree of smart organizations	Between Groups	15.212	5	3.042	6.715	.000
	Within Groups	100.589	222	.453		
	Total	115.800	227			

The following table shows the existence of statistically significant differences according to the macro variable in the dimensions of the smart organization in all dimensions and the total score. This confirms the validity of the hypothesis, and to know the direction of differences, the LSD test was used as follows:

Table 13: Results of the LSD Test for the direction of differences and their significance in the strategic vision after reference to the macro variable

College	CIS	UCAS	CCA	PTC	GTC
CIS	-				
UCAS	0.482468*	-			
CCA	-0.212746	-0.695214*	-		
PTC	0.282675	-0.199793	0.495421*	-	
GTC	0.043043	-0.439424*	0.255790	0.239631	-
CST	0.128995	-0.353473*	0.341742*	-0.153680	0.085952

* Function at level of significance (0.05)

From the above table, there are differences in strategic vision between UCAS and CIS, CCA, GTC and UCAS. The results showed differences between PTC and CCA for PTC and differences between PTC and CST for CST.

Table 14: Results of the LSD test for the direction of differences and their significance in the culture of merit and skill due to the macro variable

College	CIS	UCAS	CCA	PTC	GTC
CIS	-				
UCAS	0.388683*	-			
CCA	-0.444451*	-0.833134*	-		
PTC	0.196758	-0.191925	0.641209*	-	
GTC	-0.002320	-0.391004*	0.442130*	-0.199078	-
CST	-0.039606	-0.428289*	0.404845*	-0.236364	-0.037285

* Function at level of significance (0.05)

From the previous table, there are differences in the culture of merit and proficiency between the University College of Applied Sciences (UCAS), the CIS, the CCA, the GTC and the UCAS. The results showed that there were differences between PTC and CCA for PTC, GTC and CCA differences for GTC and differences between CST and CCA for CST.

Table 15: Results of the LSD Test for the direction of differences and their significance after the incentive program due to the macro variable

College	CIS	UCAS	CCA	PTC	GTC
CIS	-				
UCAS	0.361801*	-			
CCA	-0.396361*	-0.758162*	-		
PTC	0.140269	-0.221532	0.536630*	-	
GTC	0.099563	-0.262239	0.495923*	-0.040707	-
CST	-0.030185	-0.391987*	0.366175*	-0.170455	-0.129748

* Function at level of significance (0.05)

From the previous table, there are differences in the incentive program between the UCAS and the CIS, the CCA and the UCAS. The results also showed differences between CIS and CCA in favor of CIS. The results also showed differences between PTC and CCA for PTC, GTC and CCA differences for GTC, Between CST and CCA for CST,

Table 16: Results of the LSD Test for the direction of differences and their significance in the total score of the smart organization due to the macro variable

College	CIS	UCAS	CCA	PTC	GTC
CIS	-				
UCAS	0.412691*	-			
CCA	-0.349479*	-0.762170*	-		
PTC	0.208274	-0.221532	0.557753*	-	
GTC	0.048469	-0.364222*	0.397948*	-0.159805	-
CST	0.021442	-0.391249*	0.370921*	-0.186833	-0.027027

* Function at level of significance (0.05)

From the previous table, there are differences in the total smart score between UCAS and all other colleges in favor of UCAS. The results also showed differences between CIS and CCA in favor of CIS. The results also showed differences between PTC and CCA for PTC, GTC and CCA differences for GTC, Between CST and CCA for CST, Based on the above results, it is clear that the most applied colleges are the UCAS and the least applied is the College of the Far East (CCA)

Third hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences at the level of a ≤ 0.05 in the dimensions of the smart organization according to the functional level variable

Table 15: Analysis of the single variation of One Way Anova to find differences in the dimensions of the organization smart according to the variable level of employment

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Strategic vision	Between Groups	1.297	5	.259	.503	.774
	Within Groups	114.548	222	.516		
	Total	115.845	227			
Culture of merit and craftsmanship	Between Groups	2.298	5	.460	.706	.620
	Within Groups	144.554	222	.651		
	Total	146.852	227			
Incentive Program	Between Groups	.962	5	.192	.266	.931
	Within Groups	159.656	221	.722		
	Total	160.618	226			
Overall degree of smart organizations	Between Groups	.567	5	.113	.219	.954
	Within Groups	115.233	222	.519		
	Total	115.800	227			

The above table shows that there are no differences in the technical faculties of the dimensions of the organization smart according to perceptions of the level of employment in these colleges.

12. CONCLUSIONS

1. The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of the smart organization and a relative weight (71.42%) according to the perspective of the employees of the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip.
2. The results of the study showed a high level of smart organizations (strategic vision, culture of merit and skill, incentive program) in technical colleges in the Gaza Strip, where the field (culture of merit and proficiency) ranked first and with relative weight (73.76%), in the second place came the field (strategic vision) and relative weight (72.62%), finally, the field of incentive program came in third and last place with relative weight (67.91%).
3. The results showed that there are differences between the faculties in the dimensions of the smart organization, where it was found that the most colleges applied to the dimensions of the smart organization is the University College (UCAS) and the least applied is the College of the Far Society (CCA).
4. The results showed that there are no differences in perceptions of different functional levels to apply the dimensions of the smart organization.

13. RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings of the researcher, he recommends the following:

1. Enhance the dimensions of the smart organization in the technical colleges by working to improve the incentive program, develop the strategic vision and then support the culture of merit and skill.
2. Urge the senior management and decision makers of the technical colleges to create, innovate and reward and support their creators.

REFERENCES

- [1] El Talla, S. A., Abu Naser, S. S., Abu Amuna, Y. M., & Al Shobaki, M. J. (2017). The Reality of Technical Education in Palestine, International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS), 1(10),102-117.
- [2] Abu Amuna, Y. M., Al Shobaki, M. J., & Abu Naser, S. S. (2017). Strategic Environmental Scanning: an Approach for Crises Management. International Journal of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering, 6(3), 28-34.
- [3] Abu Naser, S. S., & Al Shobaki, M. J. (2017). The Impact of Senior Management Support in the Success of the e-DMS. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS), 1(4), 47-63.
- [4] Abu Naser, S. S., Al Shobaki, M., & Ammar, T. M. (2017). Impact of Communication and Information on the Internal Control Environment in Palestinian Universities. International Journal of Hybrid Information Technology, 10(11), 41-60.
- [5] Abu Naser, S. S., El Talla, S. A., Abu Amuna, Y. M., & Al Shobaki, M. J. (2017). Technical Education and its Role in Promoting Entrepreneurship in the Gaza Strip. Paper presented at the Second Scientific Conference on Sustainability and enhancing the creative environment of the technical sector Palestine Technical College - Deir Al Balah 6-7 December 2017.
- [6] Abu Naser, S. S., El Talla, S. A., Abu Amuna, Y., & Al Shobaki, M. (2017). Social Networks and Their Role in Achieving the Effectiveness of Electronic Marketing of Technical Colleges. Paper presented at the Second Scientific Conference on Sustainability and enhancing the creative environment of the technical sector Palestine Technical College - Deir Al Balah 6-7 December 2017.
- [7] Al-Abadi, Hashem Fawzi (2012). Organizational Intelligence as a Business Practice towards Building a Smart Organization - A Conceptual Perspective, 11th Annual Scientific Conference, Business Intelligence and Knowledge Economy, Jordan Zaytoonah University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, 23-26 April 2012, Amman Jordan.
- [8] Al-Abd, Abdul Rahim (2001). Technical Education in Palestine and a Course on Development, Journal of Vision, State Information Service, Palestine, Gaza Issue 11.

- [9] Al-Faraj, Mohamed Samir and Al-Zubayr, Osman (2011). "The Smart Organization and the Five Pillars of the Future Organization, Arab Organization for Administrative Development, Cairo, Egypt, p.
- [10] Al-Issa, Ahmed Mohammed (2004). The Future of Technical Education in the Arab Gulf Countries in the Light of Modern Trends, Journal of Educational Research, Third Year, First Issue, National Center for Educational Research and Development, January 2004, p. 131.
- [11] Al-Kasasbeh Mohammed Mufaddy, Al-Kasasbeh, Saleh Alshekh Mohammad & AL-Faouri, Abeer Hmoud, (2016). Smart Organization Characteristics and its Impact on Social and Environmental Performance: An Empirical Study on Jordan Phosphate Mines Company, International Journal of Business and Management; Vol. 11, No. 8; 2016
- [12] Al-Saeed, Mohammed Amal (2006). Report on the Egyptian Technological Colleges Project, September 2006, Egypt.
- [13] Al-Shahry, Abdullah Ali Abdullah (1995). Administrative and Educational Status in Technical Colleges in Saudi Arabia, Master Thesis (Unpublished), Umm Al Qura University, Makkah Al Mukarramah, KSA.
- [14] Al-Taei, Yousef Hageem Sultan and Janabi, Sajjad Mohammed Attia and Al-Sabahawi, Amer Abdul Karim (2016). "Management of Wisdom and its Role in Achieving Sustainability for Business Organizations - An Analytical Study of the Views of a Sample of Leadership in the University of Kufa".
- [15] Ammar, T. M., Al Shobaki, M. J., & Abu Naser, S. S. (2017). The Efficiency Extent of the Internal Control Environment in the Palestinian Higher Educational Institutions in Gaza Strip. International Journal of Digital Publication Technology, 1(2), 107-126.
- [16] Badwan, J. J., Al Shobaki, M. J., Abu Naser, S. S., & Abu Amuna, Y. M. (2017). Adopting Technology for Customer Relationship Management in Higher Educational Institutions. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS), 1(1), 20-28.
- [17] Earth Policy Institute Natural Systems. (2009). www.earth-policy.org, Data Center. Retrieved on: 2009-11-07.
- [18] El Talla, S. A., Abu Naser, S. S., Abu Amuna, Y. M., & Al Shobaki, M. J. (2017). The Creative Environment and Its Relationship to the Lean Management of Technical Colleges Operating in Gaza Strip. Paper presented at the Second Scientific Conference on Sustainability and enhancing the creative environment of the technical sector Palestine Technical College - Deir Al Balah 6-7 December 2017.
- [19] El Talla, S. A., Abu Naser, S. S., Abu Amuna, Y. M., & Al Shobaki, M. J. (2017). Technical Colleges as Smart Organizations and their Relationship to Sustainability. Paper presented at the Second Scientific Conference on Sustainability and enhancing the creative environment of the technical sector Palestine Technical College - Deir Al Balah 6-7 December 2017.
- [20] El Talla, S. A., Al Shobaki, M. J., Abu Naser, S. S., & Abu Amuna, Y. M. (2017). The effectiveness of a training program in increasing crowd funding awareness. International Journal of Advanced Educational Research, 2(1), 31-37.
- [21] European Commission, PCM (2004). "Project cycle management guidelines ", Aid Delivery Methods.
- [22] Hila, A. A. A., Shobaki, M. J. A., & Naser, S. S. A. (2017). The Effect of Academic Freedoms in Enhancing the Social Responsibility of Palestinian University Staff in the Gaza Governorates. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS), 1(5), 22-35.
- [23] Japan International Cooperation Agency JICA, (2004). Guidelines for Project Evaluation Practical Method for Project Evaluating, Department office of evaluation planning coordination.
- [24] Matheson, D., & Matheson, J. E. (2001, Jul/Aug). Smart organizations perform better. Research technology management, 49-54.
- [25] Mustafa, Ahmed (2001). Outputs of Vocational Training and Labor Market in Arab Countries, Amman: Arab Center for Training and Training of Trainers, Jordan.
- [26] Pharaoh, Muhammad et al., (2015). The development of a pilot strategy for the development of the model of smart organizations applied research in mobile telecommunications companies in Iraq (Zein Iraq-Asakil-Cork), Al-Ghari Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences, University of Kufa, Al-Arq, Volume 10, No. 33 (2015) 137.
- [27] Poulsen, Kirsten M. and Arthur, Michael B.; May (2005). Intelligent Career Navigation. American Society for Training and Development. Vol. 59 Issue 5, Pp 77-79. Cited on 24th May 2006. Available: EBSCO host. Html.
- [28] Quinn, James Brain (2005). The Intelligent Enterprise a New Paradigm. Academy of Management Executive, Vol. 19, No. 4